

A PROPOSED TEXTILE FREQUENCY SELECTIVE SURFACE (FSS) FOR MULTI-BAND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract - This summary aims to propose a Frequency Selective Surface (FSS) capable of filtering multiple frequency spectra. In telecommunications, the use of equipment operating in different frequency bands is becoming increasingly common, resulting in signal saturation. Therefore, this article aims to propose an FSS capable of filtering spectra that operate in the Wi-Fi WLAN range of 2.4 GHz and Bluetooth technology, as well as operating in the 5G technology range (3.4 GHz to 3.7 GHz), and finally, in the Safety Band (5.850 GHz to 5.925 GHz).

Keywords: FSS; MultiBand; Wi-fi Wlan; 5G; Safety Band.

INTRODUCTION

Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSS) are structures that act as frequency filters, consisting of a two-dimensional periodic structure mounted on a dielectric substrate, capable of filtering one or more signals of interest [1]. FSS can be classified into aperture-type elements (inductive FSS) that function as, and also into conductor-type elements (capacitive FSS), which act as notch filters [2].

The present article proposes a FSS (Frequency Selective Surface) aimed at filtering multiple frequency bands, capable of filtering in the frequency spectrum of Wi-Fi 2.4 GHz, which operates between 2.4 GHz and 2.485 GHz [3], following the IEEE 802.11 b/g/n standard. Additionally, it operates as a filter for Bluetooth technology, which works in the frequency range of 2.4 GHz to 2.4835 GHz [4]. Similarly, capable of operating in the mid-band range of 5G technology (n77) [5], [6], which operates between 3.4 GHz and 3.7 GHz, and finally, functions as a selector in the frequency spectrum of Safety Band technology [7], which uses the frequency range between 5.850 GHz and 5.925 GHz.

DEVELOPMENT

In this work, the proposed FSS was developed computationally. Consisting of repetitions of concentric rings with the same growth ratio, introduced into a square-shaped structure. Figure 1 presents a unit cell of the proposed structure.

Figure 1. Unit cell with element geometry

The structure is defined by four concentric rings, which in the analysis have conventionally been designated as follows: the outermost ring is referred to as the first ring, the middle one as the second ring, and the innermost one as the third ring, additionally, the structure has a circumference at the center, which will be referred to as the central circumference.

In this way, the outermost square has a side length of 44.2mm, and the first ring has a radius of 19.55mm and a spacing of 4.25mm. Subsequently, the second ring has a radius of 14.45mm and a spacing of 5.95mm. Finally, the third ring has a radius of 8.5mm and a spacing of 5.95mm. The gap between each of the rings is 0.85mm. Additionally, the structure has a fourth open circle at the center with a radius of 2.55mm.

The proposed structure has a periodicity of 44.2mm, and the material used was Wool+PA with a thickness of 1.47mm, having a dielectric constant of 1.529 and a loss tangent of 0.0052. The FSS was cascaded with 15mm of air, as can be seen in Figure 2, this technique aims to increase the bandwidth of the transmission coefficient response.

Figure 2. Cascaded FSS Element

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The computational method used to perform the simulations was the method of moments (MOM). Examining the results, it is possible to observe the independence of polarity, meaning that the structures exhibit similar results regardless of the field in which the wave occurs. Figure 3 presents the results for the single-layer simulation.

Figure 3. Results obtained in terms of transmission coefficient (TH, TE) for the single-layer FSS

When analyzing Figure 3, it can be observed that the structure presents a first filtering band, using -10 dB as the insertion loss level, starting at 2.28 GHz and ending at 2.49 GHz, with its resonance frequency at 2.40 GHz (-33.03 dB). Accordingly, the structure is capable of filtering the 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi frequency band, which ranges from 2.4 GHz to 2.485 GHz following the IEEE 802.11 b/g/n standard. Additionally, the structure can filter the frequency band used by Bluetooth, which ranges from 2.4 GHz to 2.483,5 GHz.

It can also be noted that there are two other bands present in Figure 3. The second frequency band starts at 3.41 GHz and ends at 3.71 GHz, with a resonance frequency of 3.55 GHz (-37.55 dB). Meanwhile, the third band starts at 5.87 GHz and ends at 6.23 GHz, with a resonance frequency of 6.05 GHz (-29.54 dB). Therefore, the second frequency band is capable of partially filtering the mid-band used in 5G technology (Band 77), known as the C-Band, which operates in the frequency range between 3.30 GHz and 3.80 GHz, utilizing the range of 3.4 GHz to 3.70 GHz in some countries. In the same way, the third band is capable of partially filtering the frequency range of the 5.9 GHz technology or Safety Band (IEEE 802.11p), which is used for vehicle communication systems, starting at 5.850 GHz and ending at 5.925 GHz.

When examining the multilayer structure, it is possible to observe an increase of 16 MHz in the second frequency band, starting at 3.37 GHz and ending at 3.83 GHz. Additionally, there was an increase of 12 MHz in the third frequency band, starting at 5.69 GHz and ending at 6.17 GHz. In this way, as seen in Figure 4, the multilayer structure proved to be effective in completely filtering the mid-band of 5G technology used in some countries, as well as the 5.9 GHz technology (Safety Band).

Figure 4. Results obtained in terms of transmission coefficients (TH, TE) for the multilayer FSS.

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